

EMPOWERING COMMUNITIES: WOMEN'S ROLE IN PEACEBUILDING THROUGH LEARNING

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A B S T R A C T	K E Y W O R D S
<p>Globally, women play diverse and agentic roles in advocating for peace, social justice, and community well-being, addressing issues such as violence, poverty, food insecurity, and health inequities. Their engagement is often motivated by lived experience or a perceived need to create positive change. While women have a long-standing tradition of integrating learning with leadership in community development, scholarship in adult education has rarely focused explicitly on women's peacebuilding efforts. This study examines women as both learners and leaders in peacebuilding, highlighting the ways in which learning occurs for and through their peace-oriented practices. By exploring women's experiences, motivations, and strategies in grassroots peace efforts, the research identifies key insights for designing and implementing peace education programs that are responsive, contextually relevant, and effective in supporting women's learning. Understanding these learning processes not only contributes to theoretical frameworks in adult education and peace studies but also informs practical approaches to enhancing women's capacity to foster sustainable peace in their communities.</p>	<p>Women; Peacebuilding; Community learning; Adult education; Social justice</p>

Introduction

Globally, women engage in a multiplicity of agentic roles advocating to end violence and poverty, address food insecurity and health inequity, and for peace and social justice in their communities, to name a few of the concerns addressed by women (Anderlini, 2007; Boulding, 1995; Cook-Huffman & Snyder, 2017; Neustaeter, 2015, 2020; Porter, 2013). Their involvement comes from an experienced or perceived need and the desire to do something about it (Dominelli, 2019; Cook-Huffman & Snyder, 2017; Neustaeter, 2015, 2016). Women have a long tradition of merging learning and leading community change (Clover, Butterwick, & Collins, 2016; Daniels, 2003; English & Irving, 2015; Stromquist, 2015); however, this adult education scholarship rarely explicitly focuses on peacebuilding. Women's peacebuilding is a significant and under-examined learning site (Neustaeter, 2016). Recognizing and understanding the learning that happens for and through peacebuilding can support efforts to design and implement peace education programs for women that are responsive to their experiences and effective for their learning (Neustaeter, 2016, 2020).

This study grew out of a curiosity stemming from my earlier doctoral study on women's community peacebuilding in rural Manitoba, Canada (Neustaeter, 2016). Admittedly, while serene images of open sky vistas and rolling fields may conjure ideas of 'peace and quiet', the Canadian prairies do not immediately evoke images of peacebuilding. By applying a feminist concept of peace as the absence of direct, structural, and cultural violence, and the presence of social justice and caring, we can understand peace as dynamic and more than "not war", as well as understanding that peacebuilding is more than stopping war or achieving the peace agreement (Boulding, 2000; Galtung, 1969, 1990; Vellacott, 2000). In response to violence and injustice, people dream, organize, strategize, and engage in activities to reduce violence and build peace to create the communities they wish to live in. Peacebuilding is a complex multi-dimensional project that can happen on many levels, including but not inclusive to international, regional, national, organizational, and group levels. The study described here focuses on women's work to build peace at the local community level.

I come to this research as a cis-gendered, heterosexual, rural woman settler of European descent who has lived and worked mostly in Canada. I have taught in different countries and in academic and community programs. Women's community involvement has been a constant force in every community I have visited or worked, from Singapore to Sweden, Pakistan to Germany, and Jamaica to Croatia. Looking closely at my own experience, I see that the women in my family, past and present, have been or were community-involved, mostly through their churches, community clubs, or children's schools. Through my observations as a volunteer addressing local needs and issues, I note women working in paid and unpaid work to address violence and injustice and build peace. In 2018, when I started working at the International

Centre for Women's Leadership at Coady Institute (the Coady) in Antigonish, Canada, I reflected on the questions informing my earlier doctoral study, including: how do women learn to build peace in their communities? This time, my questions could be answered by women graduates of the women's leadership programs of the Coady from other countries.

Founded in 1959, Coady Institute is "an adult education organization with the mission to work with community development practitioners around the world to create positive social change in their communities" (den Heyer, Smith, & Irving, 2017, pg. 1). The institute grew out of the Antigonish Movement which combined community engagement, non-formal adult education and economic development through consumer, producer, and housing cooperatives and credit unions to address the harsh socio-economic conditions in Nova Scotia, Canada, in the early 1900s (Dodoro & Pluto, 2012). The work and success stories of the Antigonish Movement spread, and soon people were coming from the USA, England, South Africa, and other countries to see what was happening. Currently, there are over 10,000 Coady graduates from 154 counties (Coady Institute, 2024). The institute focuses on four thematic areas: Asset-Based Community Development; Building Resilient Communities; Participation, Accountability and Governance; and Strengthening Local Economies. Its work has three main constituencies: Indigenous leadership; women's leadership; and youth leadership (Coady Institute, 2024). Education programs are online or in-person at the institute in Antigonish, Nova Scotia, Canada or delivered with a local partner on-location in another country or Canadian province.

The International Centre for Women's Leadership at the Coady was established in 2011 in recognition of the direct and indirect impacts of gender justice and equity and women's participation in leadership and decision-making. This centre focuses on education and partnerships to support women's leadership for positive social change (Coady Institute International Centre for Women's Leadership, nd). Graduates of the International Centre for Women's Leadership at the Coady work on complex issues such as gender justice, human rights justice,

accountable governance, and economic development, in their communities around the globe. Their work reflects the diverse ordinary and extraordinary ways women engage in building peace in their communities, though this work may not be explicitly labeled peacebuilding. The Coady also partners with organizations around the world to collaborate on projects aligned with the institute's themes and constituencies, for example, the ENGAGE project (funded by Global Affairs Canada) - a collaboration with five organizations based in India, Bangladesh, Ethiopia, Tanzania, and Haiti, working on building women's leadership in contextually relevant ways and sectors in each country while building trans-local learning and development practice (Coady Institute Engage, 2024).

While working as a program teaching staff in the International Centre for Women's Leadership from 2018-2022, I met women engaged in community development from many communities and contexts, as well as sectors around the world. Through discussions, I began to learn about the nuances of women's community peacebuilding. What continued to stand out are the differences and similarities of women's community care work. Gender-based violence is a global reality that manifests in similar and dissimilar ways in different socio-cultural political contexts around the world. Also, the participants and graduates I spoke with revealed that we come from communities supported by traditions of women's community carework.

In the women's leadership programs, we did a herstories activity where participants break up into groups and do research on women's history focusing on women's rights, advocacy, and leadership across five centuries and around the world. Groups presented their findings to the class. A common observation shared during the activity is that it is not easy to find 'what women did', particularly prior to the 1950s, that women's accomplishments in some locations are easier to find than in other locations. For example, the differences between societies with written or oral traditions, and recognizing that in an English-dominant academic institution, records in other languages are harder to find. These challenges of access to documentation sparked rich discussions about who records what happened, who and what determines what is and is not written, who decides what is (historically) relevant, and the minimalization and silencing of women's lives and work throughout history. Looking at the written artifacts (hardcopies and digital), highlights a particular narrative, typically a male focused one, in addition to White, Western, and English. To find women's narratives, one often must go beyond the popular or mainstream narratives which are easier to access in one's context. Evidence of women's stories, work and achievements can be limited, sparse, and exclusive. The class activity inevitably would lead us to discuss the power of the narrative, the importance of counter-narratives, and recording and sharing our own stories for present and future generations.

The proverb, shared by Chinua Achebe, "until the lions have their own historians, the history of the hunt will glorify the hunter" (Brooks, 1994) resonates. Throughout history, women have often been the lions, and their stories have been told or not told by the hunters embedded in systems of sexism and patriarchy. It is not that women were not telling their stories—many women were—yet often their stories were destroyed, dismissed, debated, or labeled delusional or the exception rather than exceptional or even ordinary. A similar trajectory exists for women's community work, including, as discussed in this article, their work in resolving conflicts, caring for individual and community well-being, and addressing violence, insecurity, and injustice: in other words, community peacebuilding. Thankfully, more storytellers and researchers are highlighting and examining women and peacebuilding and the ongoing advocacy and awareness raising on women's roles in and experiences of conflict, war, and peace.

Herein lies my interest in women's history and storytelling, and my journey to tell the stories of women, families, communities, and societies from multiple perspectives to give a more complete and accurate account of what

happened. In pursuing this research, I decided to be more explicit about peace for two reasons. First, in the women's leadership programs at the Coady, peace and conflict are a topic of discussion, participants are exposed to a concept of peace that is broader than the 'peace as the absence of war' discourse, and, for many, a connection would have been made to their work in their Coady courses. Their experiences and knowledge highlight both leadership and learning for peacebuilding and affirm peacebuilding as a significant learning site (Neustaeter, 2016). Second, in late 2018 when the plan for the study was forming, the upcoming 20th anniversary of the United Nations Security Council Resolution 1325 (UNSCR 1325) on October 31, 2020, was the impetus for examining women's stories of community peacebuilding. The UNSCR 1325, was the first of ten resolutions informing the Women, Peace and Security Agenda, and a long hard-fought achievement by civil society actors and activists to recognize the gendered realities of violence, security, and peace. The intention was to divert some of the attention from the international and national discussions to community actors and realities. A study on women's peace learning would be timely.

As in previous research, I wanted to focus on what women are doing, why and how, as well as how they learn to do this (Neustaeter, 2016). In 2019, during interviews with participants, the discussions captured their knowledge and experience up to that point in time. Listening to women, who do ordinary and extraordinary things, tell their stories – often for the first time, is a gift that leaves me awed, humbled, and excited. I also feel a sense of responsibility to handle and share their stories with the world with care. Some of the participants live in very precarious situations where gender, peace and violence and security realities are drastically different from my own. It is important for me to reflect on my own biases and assumptions when it comes to women's peace practice in diverse contexts.

Literature Review

Around the world, in the areas of war, insecurity, violence, discrimination, injustice, or a combination of these, women's community work continues to be significant to the well-being of families, communities, and individuals. Feminist researchers have argued and identified how war, violence, and insecurity are gendered; simultaneously, so are peacebuilding, humanitarian aid, and reconstruction (Davies & True, 2019). In 2020, many advocates of and women peacebuilders marked the 20th anniversary of the United Nations Security Council Resolution 1325 (UNSCR 1325) which globally recognized the gendered nature of peace, violence, and security, and women's contributions to addressing violence and security and building peace (Davis & True, 2019). UNSCR 1325 was significant, as it was the first of 10 resolutions to set the women, peace, and security agenda, and it called for countries to set their own National Action Plans for implementing the resolutions. This anniversary presented a reckoning of the changes that have and have not taken place since the passing of UNSCR1325 and called for further action to support women peacebuilders around the world, the United Nations, countries' National Action Plans, and civil society (Longhurst, 2021; Newby & O'Malley, 2021; Women's International League for Peace and Freedom, 2020). The anniversary coincided with the COVID-19 pandemic, which in many regions unraveled long and hard fought for rights for women and girls. It also exacerbated gender insecurities and violence leading to what became known as the 'shadow pandemic', the increase in gender-based violence because of the government and institutional responses and measures to the COVID-19 pandemic response (United Nations, April 9, 2020). At the same time, around the world, societies' dependence on women's care work grew, and the significance of this continuous, often invisible, community care work was recognized, if only temporarily (Hamilton, Mundkur & Sheppard, 2021).

Peace is more than the absence of war. Understandings, values, and practices of peace are contextual, informed by personal, group and societal experiences, and narratives (Neustaeter, 2016, 2020). Peace comprises complex and dynamic concepts and processes at the individual, local, societal, national, and international levels (Anderlini, 2007; Dayton & Kreisberg, 2009; Mac Ginty & Williams, 2009; Webbel & Galtung, 2007). On the one hand, negative peace simultaneously includes the absence of physical violence and fear of violence as well as the presence of cultural and structural violence. On the other hand, positive peace is the presence of social justice (Confortini, 2006; Galtung, 1969): “Positive peace is the attitudes, institutions and structures that create and sustain peaceful societies.” (Institute for Economics and Peace 2018, p.5). A feminist concept of peace also considers the ethics and practices of caring, interconnectedness, and social justice; this feminist concept recognizes that peace addresses conflict in holistic, respectful, and responsible means while focusing on relationships and building understanding. As well, peace is a dynamic, not static, transformative process (Brock-Utne, 1989; Neustaeter, 2016).

Globally, women engage in a multiplicity of agentic roles advocating for peace in their communities (Anderlini, 2007; Ball, 2018; Donahoe, 2018; Flaherty, 2012; Flaherty, Byrne, Tuso, & Maytok, 2015; Hassan & Silong, 2008). Their involvement comes from an experienced or perceived need and the desire to do something about it (Ball, 2018; Dominelli, 2019; Flaherty, 2012). Women are recognized as crucial and competent actors in building peace, in post-war (Schnabel & Tabyshalieva, 2012) and post genocide (Hunt, 2017), and in peace processes and negotiations (O’Reilly, Súilleabháin, & Paffenholz, 2015), and women’s community peacebuilding (Ball, 2018; Donahoe, 2018). Yet, their expertise and efforts are seldom recognized or translated into positions of decision-making power (Flaherty et al., 2015; Hunt, 2017).

Through their private and public caring, women engage in learning through which they negotiate knowledge and develop skills and resources that sustain and develop families, communities, humanity, and themselves (Clover, Butterwick, & Collins, 2016; English & Irving, 2015). Women have a long tradition of merging learning and leadership for social and community change (Clover et al., 2016; English & Irving, 2015); however, rarely does scholarship explicitly focus peacebuilding. Peacebuilding is a significant and under-examined learning site (Neustaeter, 2016).

Every day in urban, rural, remote, suburban, inner-city, war, post-war, new democracies and more contexts, women perform everyday public acts of caring in their communities to meet the needs of children, families, individuals, communities, and women themselves (Anderlini, 2007; Mazurana & McKay, 2001; Neustaeter, 2016). Writing about the significance of women’s everyday peacebuilding to humanity, Elise Boulding (1995, p. 410) stated,

What tends to be ignored is the historical reality that women’s work of feeding, rearing, and healing humans and of building and rebuilding households and communities under conditions of constant change – including war, environmental catastrophe, and continual push-pull migrations – produced resources and skills within women’s cultures that have been critical not only to human survival but to human development.

El-Bushra (2007) and Mazurana and McKay (2001) identify that women’s peacebuilding ideas and practices include psychosocial, creative, relational, and spiritual elements, which acknowledge and reflect the everyday lived experiences of individuals and communities. Rankin (2002) identifies women’s local-level change practice as “politics by another means” (pg. 1). Women’s community peacebuilding experiences and initiatives are rooted in the local context far away from the elite-level peace players and processes, such as high-level diplomacy and peace-treaty negotiations.

Leadership for women is a complex term with diverse understandings. According to Brown (2018), leadership is not about formal roles or hierarchies, authority, dominance, prominence, or being vocal. Brown (2018) defined a leader as “anyone who takes responsibility for finding the potential in people and processes, and who has the courage to develop that potential” (p. 4). Similarly, Brookfield and Preskill (2009) identified leadership as “a relational and collective process in which collaboration and shared understanding are axiomatic to getting things done” (p. 4). In communities, women have proven themselves as leaders, bringing socio-cultural, economic, and political positive change while facing significant challenges and obstacles (Ball, 2018; Donahoe, 2018; Hunt, 2017). Yet, we do not know a great deal about their diverse leadership journeys and processes of learning to be leaders, particularly in peacebuilding. This project seeks to address this gap through collecting women’s oral histories of learning to be leaders of peacebuilding.

Patriarchy, the dominant gender system, typically constructs and perpetuates the image of women as passive and dismisses and suppresses women’s agentic roles. Patriarchy manifests similarly and uniquely in local contexts, informing and informed by local gender ideologies and values. Knowing their local sociocultural contexts via their own situated experiences, women develop relevant and effective responses to community needs and challenges. In doing so, women negotiate situated peacebuilding practices and knowledge responsive to their sociocultural geographies. Drawing upon the legitimate female attributes of being maternal and caring, women address community needs demonstrating their skills and expertise informed by their lived experiences and determination to address local concerns and get things done.

While there is a prevalent and dominant concept of women as passive, as peacebuilders and peacemakers, women’s experiences (and roles in society, including in social issues and conflict, violence, and war) are multiple and diverse. Such an ideal concept of woman needs to be questioned as there is no universal woman. A woman may not espouse the values and goals of peace. Women often draw upon the image and expectations of socially and culturally accepted maternal and caring female attributes to motivate, legitimize, and give authority to their peacebuilding for themselves and their communities. Examining the local forms of peacebuilding, the nine women who participated in this study, intended to highlight how women manifest as peacebuilders in diverse contexts, and connect the scholarship with the everyday lives of women striving for peace at the local level.

Research Methodology and Methods

This feminist oral history study (Bornat, 2004; Gluck & Patai, 1991; Sangster, 2014) centres women’s knowledge and experience to build a deeper understanding of women community peace leaders and peace leadership learning. Feminist theory recognizes women as social actors in dynamic local-global, socio-cultural, gendered, and power contexts. It seeks to understand women’s situated experiences, knowledge, and cultures within these spaces (Naples, 2003). Oral history connects the personal and the social through storying, giving space to the tacitly held stories and knowledge told first-person acknowledging the contextual and the complex (Conle, 2000; Connelly & Clandinin, 1990; Leavy, 2011).

Semi-structured online and in-person interviews were used to collect women’s stories. This format provided a guiding structure to the conversations while simultaneously being flexible so that our conversations could veer in directions relevant to the participants. The conversational nature of the interviews allowed for a deeper narrative exploration of practice and reflection on practice. The advancement in digital communication technology allowed each participant and the researcher to connect across vast distances, local to local. Interviews were scheduled in negotiation with participants to find dates and times convenient for participants and the researcher. Interviews took place between July and December 2019. Participants took part in one two-to-three-

hour interview. Interviews were transcribed by a student research assistant and with the principal researcher analyzed for emergent themes focusing on women's peace work journeys including experiences, definitions of peace, and peace learning and leadership. Data was organized and coded in an Excel spreadsheet. Early analysis emphasized concepts of peace, their work and learning to do this work. These findings will be discussed below.

Participants

Informed by the Coady women's leadership classroom experiences and discussions on women's stories, as described above, it was decided to invite graduates of these programs to participate in the study. Participants were recruited through the institute's networks. Information about the study was sent out to women graduates with an invitation to contact the researcher for more information or express interest in participating. As the researcher was also an instructor at the Coady at the time of this study, participants could not be students in a course taught by the researcher at the time or have applied for a course the researcher would be teaching. By volunteering for this study, women self-identified as working for peace in their communities. Participation was voluntary and participants could withdraw from the study at any time without consequences. Participants did not receive a stipend for participating.

Nine women graduates of the Coady Institute, between the ages of 30 and 50, from nine countries on four continents volunteered to participate in the study. Of the participants, three were graduates of courses taught by the researcher; three were known to the researcher through Coady networks, and three were unknown to the researcher prior to the study. They were involved in diverse activities and issues including, but not limited to, Indigenous and human rights, gender-based violence, child sexual abuse, climate change, disability rights, the environment, conflict resolution, justice, and women's economic security and livelihoods. They all have at least an undergraduate degree, some have a master's degree, and one has a doctorate. They live in cities, towns, and villages. One is from a refugee camp and calls this home. One lives in a crisis/conflict zone (though it is not called a war zone). The women balance family and home roles, paid work, and volunteer work – often multiple volunteer roles, and work in numerous sectors, often simultaneously. Recognizing the diverse realities of women's security and autonomy for women to determine their security, participants chose how they wanted to be identified in this study, by their name or pseudonym. Seven women chose to be identified by their name and two chose to be identified by a pseudonym. All participants attended in-person courses at Coady Institute in Antigonish, Canada. Participants' multiple roles illustrate women's simultaneous interconnect work for peace in numerous ways and spaces of engagement. For women, their community peace work is not one identity or practice, rather, as community peacebuilders, they engage in multiple roles and activities to respond to community needs and support community peacebuilding. Their peace work reflects their personalities, strengths, and spheres of influence within their communities. They do not silo their peace work into one role or sector; rather, peacebuilding flows into all areas of their lives. For the nine women who shared their stories in this study, building peace is not a job, it is a way of being. Table 1 identifies their self-identified roles and sectors of engagement.

Table 1: Participants’ Roles and Sectors of Engagement

Participants’ Roles		Participants’ Sectors of Engagement	
Mother	Environmentalist	Criminal Justice	Social Enterprise
Daughter	Graduate Student	Human Rights	Indigenous Rights
Aunt Wife	Civil servant	Child Rights	Access to Education
Friend	Executive director	Micro-finance	Disability Rights
Colleague/coworker	Educator	Civil Service	Peace & Conflict
Filmmaker	Writer	Sustainability	Resolution
Entrepreneur	Trade Unionist	Environment	Education
Psychologist	Journalist	Community Violence	Conflict Resolution
		Prevention	Agriculture
		Research	Media

Women Learning Peace Leadership Stories

Examining the stories of the nine women participants in this study highlighted the diverse ways they engaged and learned to be peacebuilders in their communities and their learning in this journey. Recognizing the nuanced and contextual manifestations of peace, women were asked to share their definitions of peace. This is where we will begin, followed by their learning peacebuilding and thus becoming local peace leaders.

Defining peace

Participants’ understandings of peace focused on intra-personal peace, peace within oneself, interpersonal peace, and peace in society. Peace is about relationships, connection, social justice – eliminating injustice, and holistic. Several women emphasized unity in their clarification of peace, unity among people, and unity within oneself. Fati, a rural social entrepreneur whose advocacy work started in the trade unions, described peace as unity, coming together despite differences:

Peace means unity, togetherness. Then to also be able to unite and come together as one. One family. One united family. And then also understand each other, also, to also relate to each other's views. When you do that, it brings peace.

Cristina, program coordinator and community organizer, shared a definition of peace emphasizing wellbeing and connection, with self, others, community and the environment. [Peace is] a connection which is fluent, it’s not based on fear, which is not based on guiltiness. It is truly an honest connection. It’s a sense of wellbeing. It also helps me to improve everything in my life to be a better person. To work better, to not judge, to be part of the community.

Elsie, a civil servant, social entrepreneur and organizer focusing on women, peace and security and who, at the time of our conversation, was living in a militarized violent conflict, talked about peace as a way of being in the world:

It touches every human being. What I mean when I say it touches all aspects of life, from your heart to your whole being, the way you speak, the way you act, the way you react, the way you look at life, the way you use your friendships, it should all do with the word “peace.” And then we accept each other.

Kholoud, a filmmaker, photographer, and educator, noted that peace cannot exist without justice and dignity. I think to have proper active peace, we have to ensure that people wherever they are, that their dignities are being protected and they are treated as human beings—as people who have dignity and have rights at the same time. It cannot happen on the basis that people’s justice and people’s rights are degraded. ... [F]or people to have peace, it is really important to have basic human rights and one of them, for example, is the right to water.

I think the absence of these rights is a stimulator for conflict.

Shirley, a media consultant, social entrepreneur and rights activist, recounted how her idea of positive peace is informed by women who sort garbage and women farmers she has worked with who defined peace as “having food on the table.” While simple, this definition expands into a concept and practice of respect, autonomy, and agency over one’s life and family. We worked with them and at the end I said, “what does peace mean to you?” And they said peace is about having food on the table. And I was like: “Yeah! For me, it is the same thing.” ... Another thing for me is knowing about their roots and their rights. I am thinking about if you know about your roots, that gives you confidence, and your identity. And about their rights, if they need to, they will assert their rights.

Rosa, an Indigenous rights and environmental activist in Mexico, noted that peace is being able to have one’s needs met and, to meet one’s needs, their abilities and agency, and to live in a society where this is possible. Thinking about the women she works with, Rosa expressed for them, it’s to have good food, to not be struggling, to buy tomatoes and things in the market. They want the possibility to go to the market and buy their things and not just thinking all the time if they are going to have enough money to do that.

The women’s definitions of peace highlighted the significance of the individual and the collective, collaboration and unity, with respect for self and differences, and that peace is complex, requiring knowing and addressing the structural violence so that there will be food on the table. Notably, they acknowledge differences and the learning to be together with these differences. Embedded within these concepts of peace are: that peace is active, and acts within oneself, with others, and with community.

Learning Peace Leadership

Women identified peace leadership learning through experiential learning, formal or nonformal learning, and mentoring. Discussions around learning often became elusive, meaning that asking explicitly about “how did you learn” often produced short responses such as “I don’t know” or “it is just an instinct.” Christina noted, “I think that it is my call; it is my vocation. It is how I feel connected to myself. There is not a specific moment in my life—I think it’s been my whole life.” Amaka also described her peace learning as instinct. “I think it just comes like that. I keep telling myself I don’t know! But I think, firstly, I have an instinct. Secondly, part of my upbringing makes me like things like that.” When people are busy doing this work, they may not pause to think, “how did I learn to do this?” In our conversation, Christina noted that this was the first time she stopped to think about how she learned to do peacebuilding. Recognizing this ambiguity, exploring, and talking about how we have learned to do what has become our ordinary everyday work often needs to focus on specific events or tasks or stories and then digging deeper into these stories and asking about where they may have learned specific skills or concepts or processes.

Nonformal and formal learning

All participants took part in nonformal education in peace and conflict transformation and one participant had a master’s degree in peace and conflict studies. Participating in nonformal or formal education was significant for two reasons explored here. First, it exposed the women to new ideas and provided a space for reflecting on new

and old ideas to refine, expand, and deepen their practice. Second, the credential, whether a certificate, diploma or a degree, provided legitimacy and credibility to their expertise and practice. Samia, a youth and women's advocate in Egypt, took a three-day conflict transformation course which sparked her interest in integrating peacebuilding into her work.

While at Coady Institute, some of the participants took nonformal peace and conflict resolution/transformation courses; others were in courses where the topic came up. While at Coady, Fati studied development leadership, conflict transformation, adult education, and livelihoods and markets. When she got home, she pieced these together and started a local non-governmental organization supporting women's village savings and loans associations (VSLAs) in her region. Fati identified that it was the classroom learning and learning from fellow participants that led her to see what is possible:

The whole thing really, it started when I came to Coady to do the program in Development Leadership. And then after that, the course I did in peacebuilding and conflict resolution. And then I also did an adult certificate course in training and facilitation, and then advocacy. And then microfinance, so it was through microfinance we got to know about the VSLA when it was mentioned that Kenya was doing it. And they were doing it here, but it wasn't as exposed as in Kenya and Uganda and other places. When I came [home], I also started the VSLA by putting it in communities. I was also using ABCD [asset-based community development]. That was something I started—my classroom learning and then learning experiences from other participants who came from various countries. It was a lot to learn at first. I really had so many different, different, experiences.

Recognizing the potential for learning when the women's VSLAs meet, she developed and facilitated conflict resolution and peace training into the group sessions, including the use of role plays. Fati's experience at Coady and later work in communities suggest a continuum of learning that includes adapting one's learning experiences to support facilitating learning for people in communities.

Shirley summarized her reason for doing nonformal and formal learning as the ability to give back.

What pushed me is because I wanted to give back to my people. When I was in Costa Rica doing my MA, that is what really pushed me—the idea of wanting to give back to my people. Thinking if I was educated, through scholarships, and empowered to get a job and things like that. About culture, I want to be a bridge to make this possible also. To engage in these opportunities.

Reviewing their stories, education was valued and emphasized as intrinsically important to the well-being of self and communities. Sherna, reflecting on her own dreams while in an abusive marriage, discussed the importance of education for building confidence and self-worth so that one can advocate for their needs.

I thought, "I need an education." This was at the back and the forefront of my head. That is why I am so passionate about education, because, when someone is not educated, and we're speaking from the academic aspect, but also through the different literacies that exist for information sharing and acquiring, you actually feel lost. You may have certain ideas pop into your head, but you are afraid to speak them because you fear being shut down. You fear someone asking, "where did you go to school? What was your discipline?" So, that allows for self-exclusion and self-reduction because you do not feel confident enough based on the experiences you may have had to speak at certain events or certain meetings because there's this drive in society that says that to speak you have to have an academic background to be respected.

A common thread of all participants is that they are graduates of Coady Institute, where they pursued nonformal learning in an area of community development practice and leadership. While the study did not ask participants

why they chose to study at the Coady, the reality that they did, often at the significant expense of time, money, and travel, suggests the value of education and making this a priority for their peace practice.

Role Models

Participants often discussed various teachers or role models – people who did not hold an official position of teacher, yet whose example and knowledge they admired and tried to emulate. When these people were known personally to the women, they could dialogue with them on their work. In families, mothers and grandmothers were often cited as role models. Women also noted fathers and husbands, highlighting the importance of men as role models and advocates for gender equity. Community women, teachers and local politicians were also identified as examples of what people are capable of. Notably role models were known to the participants, often local women, including family members, who would have relevant expertise and experience in the same context as the participants. Describing one of her role models, Amaka, noted what she admired about a former Minister of Finance.

Every time she speaks, there is something; she's objective when she does things, she does it with sentiment. When she does things, she does it the right way. She does it with a reason to do it. No joking around, just do it the way it needs to be done. I can stand and defend her because she stands behind what she does. Just do it, just do it right. She says if you do it right, you will have no problem. From a long time ago, I have known I could learn from her. She knows how to listen. She is calm. She knows how to listen, she knows how to read contracts. She doesn't need to argue. She has a standard. She's calm, she's patient. She believes in equality. She's confident, outspoken, and strong. What she believes in is clear.

Shirley immediately identified her mother and grandmother as role models.

My mother is the most hard-working person that I know. She is always doing volunteer work, helping with whatever is happening in the community, whether at church or if there's an event. She is the first one that I remember. My grandmother is the local healer.

She's not an Indigenous person but she's kind of like that. The local healer with the spirits and things like that. I am usually with her when she's doing the offering. You do the offering to the tree, for example. You keep something that is not seen and my grandmother says we need to offer something. While she is gone, I am still in the house leading the prayer, kind of like an assistant before. I remember my grandmother. She is also one of the people who I look to when it comes to mentors. I usually ask [her] a lot of questions.

Like Shirley, and others, Rose identified her parents as role models, as well as teachers who supported critical thinking, and the people she encounters through the organization she is involved with.

I think I've learned from lots of people. I've learned to do this from looking at my mom, and my dad working with the teachers' union in my state, which is one of the braver states. I learned by looking at my aunts who are also teachers. ... I learn a lot from the peasants who are in our organization and are always asking lots of questions. They teach me a lot. I am always learning, you know?

In discussing role models, the women highlighted characteristics they value including authenticity, perseverance, strength, compassion, empathy, and more. They also noted skills they strive to incorporate into their practice, such as public speaking, active listening, advocacy and caring.

Discussion

Nine women from nine countries on four continents narrated their work for peace with and in their communities, their definitions of peace, the purpose of this work, and their learning to do and from their community peacebuilding. Across distances and over time, the nine women highlighted the nuanced and universal

understandings of peace, relevant to people in the context of their lives. They also highlighted the various ways of learning about and for peacebuilding.

Notably, this learning is multifaceted, happening simultaneously in different ways.

Women talked about the importance of exposure to community involvement, social justice, and peace work in their childhood for their current work. Growing up in a family where people, in particular women, were engaged in community care work and social justice, can result in women acquiring the critical consciousness. Donna Chovanec (2009) explains,

The idea of ‘acquiring’ critical consciousness suggests a process of passively absorbing elements (e.g., values, philosophies) from the external social structures in which one is embedded (e.g., family, community). While not conscious at the time, these early experiences establish the predisposition for developing a more robust critical consciousness in the future. (p. 39)

Memories of grandparents, parents and community members, often women, engaging in peace work, were present in all women’s interviews. Peacebuilding as an instinct may be informed by their acquiring critical consciousness and observing, throughout childhood, what is possible.

Considering that all women were graduates of a nonformal adult education institute for community development practitioners it is not surprising to see the emphasis on credentialed learning that came up in our conversations. As noted, while the motivations for pursuing these forms of education were not an area of inquiry in this study, the benefits of this education directly impact the women’s peacebuilding practice and thus their communities. The credential supports credibility and thus supports women’s community peace work. Focusing on the nonformal and formal learning, the latter which often is more highly valued, dismisses the significance and continuity of the informal learning by doing, often in cooperation with others. Recognizing the full scope of learning that informs and builds community peace practice, it is important to factor in all ways women learn as they are mutually supportive in deepening learning and practice.

In a previous study on rural Canadian women’s community peacebuilding and learning, discussions on the influence of nonformal and formal education were not prevalent. This contrasts with the current study. In the study with rural Canadian women, the participants shared a common geographical area and discussions of learning emphasized individual and group learning by doing, observation, and role models (Neustaeter, 2016). Looking at what forms of learning are emphasized raises further questions about women’s positionality and power within their contexts of practices and the influence of having this education, including the perception or narrative of education within contexts, to advance or limit their agendas for peace.

The nine women who shared their stories for this study demonstrate a small sample of the significant work women do locally in their communities to support peacebuilding and the multiple ways in which they learn to do this work. In doing so, the significance of the other forms of learning, for example, through experience and role models, are recognized. Exploring the spectrum of learning that supports this work expands the discussion of peace education beyond the formal and nonformal learning which are prevalent in adult peace education scholarship and calls for more scholarship on the multiple ways of learning about and for community peacebuilding (Bajaj, 2008; Harris & Morrison, 2003; Finley, 2011; Kekkonen, 1981; Neustaeter, 2016, 2020; Turay & English, 2008). Recognizing that women have historically and in some contexts, currently, are excluded or face obstacles to formal and nonformal education, expanding the learning narrative builds a more inclusive analysis. At the same time, scholars must be cautious of inadvertently perpetuating an exclusion argument. As

gender advocates, to disrupt the status quo, scholars can position themselves for the inclusion of women in nonformal and formal education, rather than suggesting that women's informal learning will suffice.

Conclusion

For women who shared their knowledge and experiences of building peace in this study, peace is about relationships within ourselves and others, unity, curiosity, and addressing inequity and injustice. It is much broader than the absence of war and physical and military violence. Women's peacebuilding is informed by multiple forms of learning, including experiential learning by doing, to classroom learning in nonformal and formal course and programs. Role models not only demonstrate to young girls and women that social change work is happening; they also model actions and strategies for peace work in their communities. Recognizing the diversity of ways that women engage in community peacebuilding, often simultaneously, by listening to and capturing their stories through oral history, is a way to demonstrate to others, what is possible and to build the critical consciousness that may spark others to engage in community peacebuilding.

Creating intentional accessible nonformal and formal peacebuilding learning opportunities for women will support their reflective practice, critical thinking, and analysis of their peacebuilding practice. Engaging with other women peacebuilders from their own communities and others expands the dialogue and opportunities to explore what is possible and for learning from each other. This learning builds upon learning from role models in the community who have historical reference and first-hand experience and context specific knowledge of what could be possible in community peacebuilding practice.

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